

Auditory Displays

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Deliverable Information Sheet

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1.1	23.12.24	Amedi Lab	Review 1
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Executive summary

In this report, we summarize the demonstrations of the results in the work package T4.3 (auditory displays) designed by Eurecat Audio Team (and available in the GuestXR consortium to support social interactions in XR environments). In virtual meetings, audio quality is often far from ideal. Participants connect from different remote locations, each situated in unique acoustic environments with varying levels of noise and reverberation captured by their microphones. This creates two key challenges: 1) noise from diverse environments and 2) mismatched room acoustics. To address these issues, we focus on two technical solutions: 1) speech enhancement, which improves speech clarity in noisy settings, and 2) acoustic matching, which ensures that all audio signals sound as if they originate from the same acoustic space. Below, we give a brief description of the results of our research projects in the domain of speech enhancement and acoustic matching.

For more details, please refer to the video available here: <https://youtu.be/yPt3EZROBiU>

The video is also available on GuestXR's YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@GuestXR>

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List of Demonstration

Demonstration 1: Deep learning for speech enhancement in hearing aids.

The first result focuses on enhancing speech in hearing aids. Hearing aids often struggle to reduce noise in complex settings. Traditional signal processing techniques often make unrealistic assumptions about statistical properties of speech in noise, which are not met in dynamic acoustic scenes. Using new deep-learning techniques, significant noise reduction improvements are typically observed. We tested the potential of these methods in the context of hearing aids. For that, we created a complex evaluation set up, which required generating realistic data with virtual acoustic simulations, training state-of-the-art deep-learning based noise reduction method and recording hearing aid signals with a dedicated equipment (head and torso simulator and ambisonics-based loudspeaker reproduction setup). We processed these recordings with different signal enhancement methods and compared them with several perceptual objective metrics. Advanced deep learning models outperformed traditional methods in noise reduction but introduced distortions, which affected sound quality. Balancing these trade-offs remains a key challenge. This result has been published as:

Gusó, Enric, et al. "An objective evaluation of hearing aids and DNN-based binaural speech enhancement in complex acoustic scenes." *2023 IEEE Workshop on Applications of Signal Processing to Audio and Acoustics (WASPAA)*. IEEE, 2023

[Link to the publication](#)

Demonstration 2: Improving speech enhancement with better training data.

The second result focuses on speech enhancement through improved data. Using virtual acoustic simulations, a novel dataset was created, incorporating source and receiver directivity and room acoustics. We trained a state-of-the-art speech enhancement model and compared it to a regular training results using various objective audio metrics. The results indicated a significant improvement in the performance for the proposed training scheme. The publication for this result is in preparation and will be submitted in February 2025 to ISCA Interspeech2025 Conference:

Gusó, Enric, et al. "MB-RIRs: a Synthetic Room Impulse Response Dataset with Frequency-Dependent Absorption Coefficients." *In preparation*

Demonstration 3: Deep learning for acoustic matching

This result is related to the acoustic matching problem. In augmented reality the sound of our virtual conversation partner must be seamlessly integrated into our own soundscape. We developed a deep-learning method to make speech recorded in one space sound as if it originated within another space. We measured the similarity of the signals generated with the method to the ground truth signals from the target space.

Our approach performed better than traditional signal processing methods, but more work is needed to reduce distortions and develop specific acoustic evaluation metrics. The publication for this result is in preparation and will be submitted in January 2025 to Forum Acousticum Euronoise 2025 Conference:

Luberadzka, Joanna, et al. "Conditional Wave-U-Net for Acoustic Space Transfer in Augmented Reality." *In preparation*

Demonstration 4: Evaluating speech enhancement in VR

The final result consists in integrating and testing audio technologies in virtual reality. We created a virtual sound environment that simulates a typical VR remote meeting. We conducted a pilot user study to validate our virtual acoustic scene and to assess the impact of various speech enhancement techniques on communication. Participants took part in a virtual experience, in which they were seated at a table with four avatars. They could listen to the conversation and switch between different audio processing methods with a user interface. After the experience, they were asked to rate different aspects of speech enhancement in a questionnaire.

The results of the study conducted in this virtual environment showed that only some speech enhancement methods improve communication. This study highlighted the potential of using VR as a tool to study speech communication. We plan to continue exploring this area in future research. This result has been submitted as an article to the journal *Frontiers in Virtual Reality*:

Luberadzka, Joanna, et al. "Audio technology for improving social interaction in extended reality." *In revision, Frontiers in Virtual Reality*

References

Gusó, Enric, et al. "An objective evaluation of hearing aids and DNN-based binaural speech enhancement in complex acoustic scenes." *2023 IEEE Workshop on Applications of Signal Processing to Audio and Acoustics (WASPAA)*. IEEE, 2023
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10248112>

Gusó, Enric, et al. "MB-RIRs: a Synthetic Room Impulse Response Dataset with Frequency-Dependent Absorption Coefficients." *In preparation*

Luberadzka, Joanna, et al. "Conditional Wave-U-Net for Acoustic Space Transfer in Augmented Reality." *In preparation*

Luberadzka, Joanna, et al. "Audio technology for improving social interaction in extended reality." *In revision, Frontiers in Virtual Reality*

